

RECENT SUMMER HEATWAVE IN BANGLADESH ENHANCED BY ATLANTIC MULTI-DECADAL OSCILLATION AND LARGE-SCALE ATMOSPHERIC FACTORS

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1. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of extreme temperatures and heatwaves in Bangladesh has emerged as an increasingly critical issue with significant public health implications. Empirical research suggests a disturbing trajectory of increased vulnerability to heatwaves in urban environments, particularly in metropolises such as Dhaka, where the presence of urban heat islands exacerbates prevailing conditions (Adnan et al., 2023; Tabassum et al., 2024). Health hazards are particularly acute for vulnerable populations, with mortality rates escalating during heat events (Nissan et al., 2017; Al-Mamun et al., 2023). As the impacts of climate change continue to amplify these events, the need for sustainable urban planning and adaptation practices to mitigate health threats and build resilience will become increasingly important. However, understanding the factors that triggered heatwaves in Bangladesh is still lacking. Thus, the purpose of this work is to present the physical mechanisms underlying Bangladesh's intense heat waves to identify the contributing factors to the recent heatwaves after the 2000s.

2. METHODOLOGY

The focus of this analysis was on the summer months, defined as May through September, consistent with the regional climatology following Nissan et al. (2017). The mean Tmax was calculated by aggregating the monthly values. A long-term mean summer temperature and its standard deviation were calculated over the entire study period. Anomalies for each year were computed as standardized values (z-scores, with positive anomalies indicating warmer than average summers and negative anomalies indicating cooler than average summers).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A significant climate regime shift (slope = 0.03, $p < 0.01$) is observed using a Bayesian model in the southeastern zone of Bangladesh after the 1990s (Figure 1a). There is a similar result for the northeastern zone, northern part of the northern region, northwestern zone, western zone, southwestern zone, and south-central zone (not shown). This climate regime shift (1980-2023) is associated with the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO; $r = 0.73$, $p < 0.01$) (Figure 1a). The Tmax anomaly of heatwave occurrence years (2000–2023) and AMO ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.05$) showed a significant positive association, as did the Tmax anomaly of heatwave non-occurrence years (1980–1999) ($r = 0.50$, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 1a). Results from the ERA5 reanalysis data highlight large-scale atmospheric circulation changes over the region (Figure 1 b-e). Figure 1a shows an increase in geopotential height and changes

in wind speed, indicating a strengthening of the anticyclonic circulation pattern and a weakening of the monsoon flow. Figure 1 c-d show increases in air temperature and relative humidity, respectively, indicating changes conducive to more intense heat conditions. Figure 1e shows an increase in cloud cover, suggesting increased atmospheric moisture and changes in cloud dynamics. These factors suggest that the strengthening of the anticyclonic circulation, increased geopotential height, and altered moisture and cloud conditions have significantly contributed to the observed intensification of summer heat waves in Bangladesh over the past two decades.

Figure 1: (a) The relationship between summer anomalies (Tmax) and Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation for heatwave non-occurrence (1980-1999) and occurrence years (2000-2023). Panel (b)-(e), Differences in geopotential height and wind speed (b), air temperature (c), relative humidity (d), and cloud cover (e) during MJJAS (May to September) at the 500 hPa level between the periods 1980–1999 and 2000–2023.

4. CONCLUSION

The substantial change in climate regime observed in Bangladesh after 1999, characterized by a pronounced slope and significant correlation with the AMO, highlights the vulnerability of the region to climate variability. The ERA5 reanalysis data reveal key changes in the large-scale atmospheric circulation, including enhanced anticyclonic formations, escalating air temperatures, increased relative humidity, and intensified cloudiness. These changes have cumulatively exacerbated summer heat waves in Bangladesh, underscoring the urgent need for adaptive strategies aimed at mitigating the impacts of these climatic transitions on local populations and ecosystems. Future research should prioritize the impacts of these changes and prospective adaptation strategies to strengthen resilience in the face of continued climate variability.

5. REFERENCES

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